

Teacher Communication Behavior as Determinants of Student Engagement

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Abstract: This study is aimed to find out the relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement. This study utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive technique involving teachers in Sarangani District of Davao Occidental Division, Philippines. The study was conducted on the second semester of School Year 2024-2025. Research instruments on teacher communication behavior and student engagement were used as source of data. Using mean and pearson-r as statistical tools to treat the data, the study showed the following results: the study found to exhibit a very high level of teacher communication behavior, there is a very high level of student engagement, there is a significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement. This implies that the higher the teacher communication behavior, the higher is the student engagement. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement was rejected.

Keywords: teacher communication behavior, student engagement, school administration and supervision.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers today commonly note about poor student engagement in the classroom and in school. Its common occurrence continually poses challenges among teacher which resulted to a declined student performance. These students do not see school as relevant as manifested by poor participation in performance tasks in the classroom. More so, these students do not see the importance of school as shown in their disinterest to participate in the numerous curricular and extra-curricular activities. In general, most teachers complain that their students have a little to no interest in learning which has brought the attention of teachers as it affects the student's performance in school (Gilboy, Heinerichs & Pazzaglia, 2015).

As studies revealed, the problem of student engagement in the United States is generally observed by teachers as cases on poor participation in class activities continue to soar (McClelland, Acock, Piccinin, Rhea, & Stallings, 2013). In the similar context, teachers in the Philippines also observe poor student engagement in the form of low school attendance and non-submission of homework in which teachers (Espejo, 2018). Similarly, teachers in local context also experience problem on student engagement when they pointed out that their students skip classes and habitually absent, and bring troubles in the classroom.

Meanwhile, learning environment is an indispensable component of student engagement. It molds the students to understand the relevance of engagement for their academic progress. It fosters students' interest to regularly attend classes and increase their connection to school tasks whether they are academic or extra-curricular undertakings. Also, learning environment offers opportunities for students to develop better engagement in school and eventually improve their concept about the school (Bakker, Vergel & Kuntze, 2015).

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Aside from the learning environment, the teacher communication behavior also posed a major role to boost student engagement in school activities. When teachers manifest a good sense of communication behavior, they are able to establish a communication climate that facilitates student engagement to active learning. Hence, teachers must ensure that they can communicate the lessons effectively since proper communication affect student engagement. More so, the teacher communication behavior facilitates meaningful student engagement in classroom (Wolff, Wagner, Poznanski, Schiller & Santen, 2015).

Learning environment is essential in developing student engagement. As commonly observed by most teachers, the participation rate of students in class activities increases when students are cohesive with their classmates (Gunuc & Kuzu, 2015). Similarly, teachers also noted that their communication behavior boosts student engagement. They admitted that the way they communicate their encouragement and praise to students yield an increased sense of engagement among the students in terms of high submission rate of homework and projects (Heflin, Shewmaker & Nguyen, 2017).

The importance of student engagement cannot be underestimated in the general picture of teaching and learning process. It is in the above context that the researcher would like to explore on the variables mentioned to understand better the role of other variables in developing the sense of student engagement among the learners. More so, the results of this study is aimed at contributing meaningfully to the body of knowledge regarding the variables of this research since the proponent has rarely come across with the similar study in the local context. The knowledge that can be gained from this research will definitely add to the rich available literature on the topics learning environment, teacher communication behavior, and student engagement, thereby fill in the knowledge gap regarding variables under study.

II. BODY OF ARTICLE**Statement of the Problem**

This study aimed to determine the relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement. Specifically, this study sought the answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of teacher communication behavior in terms of:
 - 1.1. challenging;
 - 1.2. encouragement and praise;
 - 1.3. non-verbal support;
 - 1.4 understanding and friendly, and
 - 1.5 controlling?
2. What is the level of student engagement in terms of:
 - 2.1. affective engagement;
 - 2.2. behavioral engagement, and
 - 2.3. cognitive engagement?
3. Is there a significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement?

Hypothesis

The following hypotheses will be treated at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement.

III. METHODOLOGY**Research Design**

This study utilized a quantitative correlational design is a type of non-experimental research design used to determine whether and to what degree a relationship exists between two or more quantifiable variables. This study will find out the significance of the relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement.

Statistical Treatment

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis of data.

Mean. This was used to determine the level of teacher communication behavior and student engagement.

Pearson r. This was used to determine the significance of the relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Teacher Communication Behavior

Shown in Table 1 is the level of teacher communication behavior with an overall mean of 4.11 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

Among the enumerated indicators, non-verbal support has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 4.14 or very high, controlling, 4.12 or very high, encouragement and praise, 4.10 or very high, understanding and friendly,

Table I. Level of Teacher Communication Behavior

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Challenging	4.09	Very High
Encouragement and Praise	4.10	Very High
Non-verbal Support	4.14	Very High
Understanding and Friendly	4.10	Very High
Controlling	4.12	Very High
Overall	4.11	Very High

4.10 or very high, and challenging, 4.09 or very high. The result of this study is aligned with the views of Kavrayıcı (2020) who posited that teacher with good communication always make the things easier and understandable. Effective communication skills are really important for a teacher in transmitting of education, classroom management and interaction with students in the class. Teacher has to teach the students having different thinking approaches. To teach in accordance with the ability and capability of the students a teacher need to adopt such skills of communication which motivate the students toward their learning process.

The result of this study is also in congruence with the statement of Claro, Salinas, Cabello-Hutt, San Martín, Preiss, Valenzuela & Jara (2018) who maintained that good communication skills of teacher are the basic need of academic success of students, and professional success of life. Teacher communicates more instructions orally in classroom to students. Teacher with poor communication skills may cause failure of students to learn and promote their academics. Student need to understand that what is right, and what is wrong while it totally depends upon the communication skills of teachers which he adopts in classroom. Good communications minimize the potential of unkind feeling during the process of teaching. For learning the learner must be attentive toward their teacher during the lecture.

Level of Student Engagement

Shown in Table 2 is the level of level of student engagement with an overall mean of 3.68 with a descriptive equivalent of very high indicating that all enumerated indicators were oftentimes observed. The overall mean was the result obtained from the mean of the indicators for the specific items from the questionnaire intended for this particular indicator which was appended in this study.

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Table II. Level of Student Engagement

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Levels
Affective Engagement	3.68	Very High
Behavioral Engagement	3.64	Very High
Cognitive Engagement	3.62	Very High
Overall	3.68	Very High

Among the enumerated indicators, affective engagement has the highest mean rating with a mean score of 3.68 or very high, behavioral engagement, 3.64 or very high, and cognitive engagement, 3.62 or very high. The result of this study is aligned with the view of Hiver, Al-Hoorie, Mercer (2020) who averred that Student engagement is a critical factor in educational success and has been widely studied in educational research. It encompasses students' involvement, motivation, and participation in their learning processes, affecting academic achievement and personal development.

Student engagement is a crucial factor in education that significantly impacts learning outcomes, academic success, and overall personal development. It encompasses students' active participation, motivation, and emotional investment in their studies. Engaged students are more likely to excel academically, persist in their studies, and develop essential life skills (Zimmermann, Stallings, Pierce & Largent, 2018).

Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Communication Behavior and Student Engagement

Illustrated in Table 3 were the results of the test of relationship between variables involved in the study. The overall correlation had a computed value of 0.108 with a probability value of $p < 0.01$ which is significant at 0.05 level. Hence the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement is rejected.

The result of the study is in congruence with the statement of Ong & Quek (2023) who believed that effective communication is the cornerstone of quality education. The way teachers interact with students, verbally, non-verbally, and emotionally, significantly influences how students respond to learning opportunities. One of the most crucial aspects of this interaction is the relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement, which encompasses behavioral, emotional (affective), and cognitive dimensions of how students involve themselves in the learning process.

Table III. Significance on the Relationship between Teacher Communication Behavior and Student Engagement

Pair	Variables	Correlation Coefficient	p-value	Decision on Ho
IV and DV	Teacher Communication Behavior and Student Engagement	0.108	0.000	Reject

This is also supported by Fatou & Kubiszewski (2018) and Konold, Cornell, Jia & Malone (2018) who posited that the connection between teacher communication behavior and student engagement is both strong and multidimensional. Effective communication fosters trust, clarity, and motivation, which in turn lead to greater student involvement, persistence, and academic achievement. When teachers communicate with empathy, enthusiasm, and clarity, they not only deliver content, they inspire students to care about their learning, participate actively, and think critically. As such, enhancing communication skills should be a top priority for educators aiming to improve student engagement and learning outcomes.

V. CONCLUSION

Based from the findings of the study, conclusions are drawn in this section. The study found to exhibit a very high level of teacher communication behavior. This means that the provisions relating to teacher communication behavior is always manifested.

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The study revealed a very high level of student engagement. This indicates that the provisions relating to student engagement are embodied in the item is always manifested.

The results of the study also confirm that there is a significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement. This implies that the higher the level of teacher communication behavior, the higher is the student engagement. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teacher communication behavior and student engagement was rejected.

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